

**UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY
AND MARKET POTENTIAL
FROM WOOD WASTE**

STRATEGIC ROADMAP

STRATEGIC ROADMAP: UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY AND MARKET POTENTIAL FROM WOOD WASTE

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Context

This Strategic Roadmap describes the current market situation and potential of wood waste in Europe, with a focus on fibreboard recycling. Nearly 47 million tonnes of wood waste were generated in the European Union in 2022. The largest source was the manufacturing sector, which accounted for 37% of total wood waste, with the wood products industry contributing about two thirds to this share. The next largest source was the waste management and water supply sector (23%), followed by the construction sector (17%). Data on utilisation are outdated and limited in detail: only around 15 million m³ (solid wood equivalent) or 40% of EU wood waste was recycled – mostly into particleboard – while the latest available JRC figures indicate that about 60% was used for energy recovery. The objective of this Roadmap is to contribute to the discussion on circular wood use, showcase current developments and upcoming solutions, and to advance wood and fibre recycling and reuse by disseminating the findings and involving key target groups, including policy makers, industry and research. It highlights challenges and opportunities and concludes with research and policy recommendations.

Initial situation

- The starting point of the EcoReFibre project has been the lack of commercially proven industrial-scale methods available for recycling fibreboard waste into new fibreboard.
- Reusing fibres in high-quality materials required new solutions across disciplines and coordinated action by industry, science, and public actors to unlock the potential for additional industrial-scale recycling across Europe.

What the EcoReFibre project delivers

- Five pilots prove advances in sorting, defibration and fibre reutilisation, reducing reliance on virgin fibres and paving the way towards the EcoReFibre ambition of reaching up to 25% recycled fibres in fibreboards.
- EcoReFibre demonstrates several industrial-scale and economically viable pathways to recycle post-consumer wood and fibreboard waste into new products, including MDF/HDF, particleboard, insulation and biocomposites.
- The EcoReFibre Strategic Roadmap aims to foster circularity and market potential from wood waste by describing the current market context, highlighting challenges and opportunities, and formulating research and policy recommendations.

The main results of the Strategic Roadmap

Key drivers and barriers

- Drivers: the need to secure raw material supply, technical progress in sorting and defibration, growing market pull, policy momentum to accelerate the circular transition, climate and jobs benefits.
- Barriers: regulatory disparities, fragmented and inconsistent collection systems, competition with energy recovery, logistical constraints, economic viability.

Based on the identified main drivers and barriers, EcoReFibre proposes three solution components, underpinned by a horizontal enabling process, to build a practical, system-level blueprint for a working circular model:

1. Design for circularity of products and components for reuse and high-value recycling, supported by recycling technologies and processes.
2. Efficient secondary-materials markets through clear specifications/standards, predictable demand, and fair conditions.
3. Secure high-quality supply at volume, i.e. clean, well-characterised fractions reaching recycling.

Horizontal enabler: sustained multi-stakeholder dialogue to foster the transition from single value chains towards a wider value network, to set common specifications, align incentives, de-risk investment, and resolve local constraints.

Research and innovation priorities

Further research and development must accelerate deployment of fibre recycling across three areas:

- Efficient secondary raw material markets: identifying, improving and scaling circular value networks for wood waste across Europe.
- Data availability: improved data systems integrating material flow, specifications, and market information.
- Technology development: optimising and further development of technologies for wood waste sorting, fibre extraction and cleaning, and panel production using recycled fibres, incl. design-for-recycling principles for fibreboards.

Policy recommendations

Policies should be aligned to increase volumes of clean, well characterised wood waste for high-value material recycling, at competitive, stable market conditions across the EU.

- Policy options to increase wood waste collection
 - Make increased wood waste collection a top priority, with flexible, locally adapted approaches across the different streams.
 - Incentivise producer takeback and reverse logistics (e.g. under Extended Producer Responsibility) linking furniture/construction products directly back to material sector.
 - Support municipal and private operators with investment for collection infrastructure and logistics.
 - Prioritise material use over energy recovery in line with the Renewable Energy Directive III's cascading principle; adjust renewable energy sources deployment to relieve pressure on woody biomass and develop non-woody biomass wastes for energy.
 - Recalibrate public support to avoid distorting competition with the material sectors.
 - Allow adequate, risk managed storage capacity (including flexible/covered options) to buffer seasonal flows and prevent loss of recyclable volumes.
- Policy options to upgrade quality of collected wood waste fractions
 - Mandate or incentivise early separation: targeted preprocessing and dismantling for furniture; selective demolition for construction and demolition waste; dedicated streams with clear labelling and advanced containers; high-control methods at civic amenity sites; reinforcement via public procurement requirements, building codes and demolition permits to make early differentiation the default option.
 - Require reinvestment of Extended Producer Responsibility funds in the continuous improvement of collection systems.
 - Scale AI/sensor-based sorting through targeted funding, public-private partnerships, or regulatory requirements.
 - Enforce preferential routing of separately collected recyclable wood to qualified material producers, to protect quality of wood waste streams and reduce leakage to lower value uses.

Conclusions

Fibreboard recycling has been proven technologically and economically viable at the industrial level.

To establish fibreboard recycling - and wood recycling for material use in general - as a working circular model, the focus must be on high-quality supply at volume and the creation of corresponding markets.

The propositions of this Strategic Roadmap are well aligned with the goals of the Bioeconomy Strategy and the upcoming EU Circular Economy Act and enable the wood panel industry to enhance its leading role in building a more resilient and competitive Europe.

1 TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

Circular wood waste terminology

Closing material loops in the wood sector involves two dilemmas regarding terminology. Firstly, the large number of terms used to precisely describe the state of wood such as virgin wood coming from the forest, industrial by-products, pre- and post-consumer wood, recovered and recycled wood, to name only a few, may confuse rather than elucidate the reader. Secondly, based on legal requirements, wood that has been used is classified as waste in many cases. At the same time, it is undisputedly a valuable resource, and to expand its use is the motivation behind EcoReFibre. Terms such as 'secondary raw material' or 'recovered wood' point in this direction but are not always applicable. Although the Waste Framework Directive [1] defines general end-of-waste criteria, no specific criteria have been implemented for wood across the EU, unlike for other waste materials. The decision when waste legally becomes a resource is therefore in the hands of national authorities.

A uniform definition cannot be derived in this situation due to differences between EU Member States. For instance, Austria is one of the few countries that have adopted national end-of-waste criteria for wood based on the Waste Framework Directive. If such national criteria do not exist, 'case-to-case' decisions are necessary to determine when a certain waste type ceases to be waste. Across Europe, the number of 'case-to-case' decisions is currently rather small, and often no related information is publicly available. Moreover, Member States remark that EU additional guidelines are needed [2].

Accordingly, besides the term 'wood waste' referring to its legal status, this roadmap uses the terms 'secondary raw material', 'recovered wood' or 'post-consumer wood' where unambiguous to designate used wood as a valuable resource of the circular bioeconomy.

Examples of national wood waste categorisations

Wood waste streams are managed differently across Europe following various national regulations and waste classifications that are mainly based on (possible) contamination level [3; 4]. For instance, Germany, Austria, Denmark, and Switzerland divide wood waste into four categories that are [4; 5; 6]:

- A I: untreated or only mechanically processed wood waste that has not been contaminated with non-wood substances to a significant degree during its use
- A II: glued, painted, coated, varnished or otherwise treated wood waste without halogenated organic compounds in the coating and without wood preservatives
- A III: wood waste with halogenated organic compounds in the coating without wood preservatives
- A IV: wood waste treated with wood preservatives, such as railway sleepers and other wood waste that cannot be classified as A I, A II or A III due to its pollutant content (wood waste treated with agents containing polychlorinated biphenyls are separately treated)

Similar systems with four classes exist in France, Belgium, and Netherlands [3; 4]. UK, Sweden, and Spain have their own wood waste categorisations, based on classes (UK) [3; 7], without classes (Spain) [3], or with a system to sort wood waste at source (Sweden) [3; 7].

A comprehensive compilation of wood waste regulations and classifications of all European countries and relevant EU-regulations is presented in the UNECE Catalogue of Wood Waste Classifications [3]. Its objective is to serve as a basis for developing a classification for the UNECE region which could serve both for data collection and as starting point for a standard facilitating wood waste trade. A summary overview of similarities and differences between those countries applying wood waste classes, based on the UNECE catalogue and additional sources, would be helpful to simplify the multi-stakeholder dialogue necessary to boost wood-waste recycling.

PROPERTY AND PROCESS TERMS	DEFINITIONS
Fibres	Wood particles with elongated shape and an average length of about 2 mm.
Fines	Wood particles with round shape and a max. dimension of about 0,3 mm or less.
WBP	Wood-based panels, general term for various types e.g. fibreboard, particleboard, oriented strand board (OSB), plywood.
MDF	Medium density fibreboard: Dry process fibreboard in accordance with EN 622-5 (650 kg/m ³ - 800 kg/m ³).
HDF	High density fibreboard: Dry process fibreboard in accordance with EN 622-5 (> 800 kg/m ³).
Hardboard	Wet process fibreboard in accordance with EN 622-2 (> 800 kg/m ³).
Defibration, extraction	Processing solid wood or fibreboard into fibres (from sources such as virgin wood, wood waste, or industrial by-products).
(m)TMP process	(Moisture modifying) Thermo-Mechanical-Pulp process, a type of defibration.

CIRCULAR WOOD AND WASTE TERMINOLOGY	DEFINITIONS
(Wood) waste	(Wood) products and materials which the holder discards or intends to discard or is required to discard, examples are discarded furniture or beams from demolition sites. This term encompasses recovered wood, post-consumer-wood (waste), and wood that is not reutilised (e.g. sent to landfill). It excludes industrial by-products such as sawmilling residues and wood to which national End-of-Waste criteria apply [1].
Secondary raw material	Obtained from waste by recycling, can replace some or all virgin material in manufacturing processes [8; 9]. In practice, it often encompasses industrial by-products (legally non-waste) and recovered wood (legally waste, unless national End-of-Waste criteria apply).
Recovered wood	Recovered wood is waste material that was collected/separated from a waste stream due to its potential for recycling; included are e.g. damaged stock and materials or products that were rejected by a manufacturer, and reclaimed post-consumer wood (such as pallets or other wood packaging material, demolition waste, used furniture)[9]. Industrial by-products are excluded [1].
Post-consumer wood (waste)	Reclaimed wood waste such as pallets, private household wood waste, used wood arising from construction or demolition of buildings or from engineering works, whether contaminated or not. It excludes material that will not be reutilised (e.g. sent to landfill) [10].
Industrial by-products	Not considered as waste, cf. Waste Framework Directive [1]. For example chips, off-cuts and sawdust resulting from the primary production process in the sawmill industry are by-products because their further use is certain, they can be used directly without any further processing other than normal industrial practice and further use is lawful [1; 11].
Recycled material	Material that has been reprocessed from recovered (reclaimed) material by means of a manufacturing process and made into a final product or into a component for incorporation into a product [12].
CDW	Construction and demolition waste.

LEGISLATIONS AND CONNECTED TERMS	DEFINITIONS
WFD	Waste Framework Directive. [1]
RED III	Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2023/2413. [13]
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (EU) 2024/1781. [14]
PPWR	Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), (EU) 2025/40. [15]
CDW Management Protocol	Construction & Demolition Waste (CDW) Management Protocol. [16]
EPR	Extended producer responsibility.
DPP	Digital Product Passport, part of the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) [14], aims to enhance transparency by providing comprehensive information about the product's origin, materials, environmental impact, and disposal recommendations.

2

INTRODUCTION

2.1 - PROJECT SUMMARY

EcoReFibre – upscaling circular use of wood waste and fibre recycling in the European wood panel industry

This Roadmap has been developed as part of the EcoReFibre project (grant no. 101057473, May 2022 to April 2026). Funded with 12 million EUR through the Horizon Europe programme, the project brings together 20 partners from 7 countries and is coordinated by the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU). Its core mission is to explore smart technologies that enable recycling of post-consumer wood back into fibreboards and novel building products. In Europe, fibreboard is mainly used for furniture (53%), laminate flooring (18%), and construction, including doors and flooring (13%). Lesser volumes are incorporated in packaging (6%), used for moulding (3%) or other applications (7%) [17].

Within the EcoReFibre project, five industry pilots demonstrate how circular economy approaches, combined with innovative and digital-supported technologies, ensure the supply of secondary raw materials. These pilots include the sorting and extraction of wood fibres and fines, and their conversion to valuable products, i.e. fibreboard and insulation products, particleboard and biocomposites. Ultimately, EcoReFibre aims to increase available wood resources in Europe through recycling. The ambition is to substitute up to 25% of the virgin fibres currently used in the European fibreboard market. The project further demonstrates how the upscaling of circular technologies can be achieved.

2.2 - STRATEGIC ROADMAP CONTEXT AND OBJECTIVES

This Strategic Roadmap on unlocking circularity and market potential from wood waste describes the current context in Europe with a focus on fibreboard recycling. Nearly 47 million tonnes of wood waste were generated in the European Union in 2022. The largest source was the manufacturing sector, which accounted for 37% of total wood waste, with the wood products industry contributing about two thirds to this share. The next largest source was the waste management and water supply sector (23%), followed by the construction sector (17%) [18]. Data on utilisation are outdated and limited in detail: only around 15 million m³ (solid wood equivalent) or 40% of EU wood waste was recycled – mostly into particleboard – while the latest available Joint-Research Centre (JRC) figures (published in 2021, referencing 2017 data) indicate that about 60% was used for energy recovery [19].

In this context, the Strategic Roadmap pinpoints challenges, drivers and barriers and sets out research and policy recommendations to support the transition from a linear to a circular economy. Its objective is to contribute to the ongoing discussion on circular wood use and showcase current developments and upcoming solutions, informing all relevant stakeholders and enabling greater wood and fibre recycling and reuse. Accordingly, the findings are shared and debated among key target groups, including policy makers, industry and the research community.

Creating a viable circular economy for wood fibre use

The EcoReFibre achievements support the EU Commission’s priority “A new plan for Europe’s sustainable prosperity and competitiveness” and its “Competitiveness Compass” [24]. They further support the European Green Deal and contribute to Europe’s sustainable growth through a more resilient circular economy in line with the upcoming EU Circular Economy Act. Notably, EcoReFibre drives the uptake of innovative, circular and bio-based materials and value chains that play a key role for the defossilisation, climate neutrality and economic autonomy in line with the updated EU Bioeconomy Strategy and the New European Bauhaus.

Despite policy ambitions for circularity, wood waste utilisation has been trending toward energy recovery, at the expense of material recycling. This Strategic Roadmap proposes how to rebalance the system to a viable circular economy that keeps wood and its derivatives in productive use, prioritising recycling and reuse over premature incineration or landfill. A key driver is the need for wood-based panel manufacturers to reduce exposure to supply risks by increasing both the share and diversity of secondary raw materials in their supply.

Building a circular economy requires a mindset shift from linear value chains towards the creation of value networks. The objective is to close material cycles without significant losses in quality or quantity as illustrated in Figure 1. Therefore, collaboration and increased dialogue among different actors are essential to identify synergies and work together towards common goals.

Figure 1: General overview of the wood material cycle for fibre recycling. EcoReFibre technologies focus on 2. sorting and 4. fibre production from recovered wood. EcoReFibre's ambition is achieving a closed material cycle and to substitute up to 25% of the virgin fibres currently used in the European fibreboard production.

Fibreboard recycling expands the options for recovered wood use

While recycling recovered wood to produce particleboard is common practice across Europe (48% of the wood in a typical particleboard made in Europe [17]), only recent technological advances have enabled industrial-scale recycling of post-consumer solid wood and fibreboard to produce new fibreboard (e.g. MDF, HDF). EcoReFibre has been instrumental in this process, particularly in sorting of recovered wood and fibre extraction from post-consumer solid wood and fibreboard. As a result, these recent technological advancements expand the options for recovered wood use to MDF that has an annual European production volume of around 11 million m³ (excluding Russia and Turkey) [17].

Across the sector, fibreboard recycling technologies are meanwhile in a fast-evolving, pre-standardisation phase, where machine manufacturers offer different solutions, particularly for defibration of post-consumer solid wood and fibreboard, and subsequent fibre cleaning. The first infrastructures are now being installed, and practice will show which concepts prove to be the most successful over time.

Viable fibreboard recycling requires sorting systems that produce high-purity fractions of recovered wood, whether from solid wood, fibreboard or other wood-based panels (WBP). This is crucial because panel manufacturing operates at large scale, feeding continuous 24/7 industrial processes with huge volumes that must consistently deliver high-quality panels meeting all performance and regulatory requirements. Impurities, such as plastic particles in the surface layer, render the semi-finished product non-compliant with quality standards and lead to its removal from further processing. In addition, separating recovered wood into high-purity fractions is an economic and environmental priority, as logistics are complex and the handling of unsorted material may increase costs and emissions. Consequently, fibreboard recycling and overall recovered wood recycling generally go hand in hand.

How to keep the resource recovered wood in a value network?

Beyond technologies, the transition from a linear to a circular economy also requires the adaptation of structures and markets to keep raw materials, such as wood, in circulation for as long as possible. To achieve this, three mutually reinforcing conditions must be met:

Design for circularity

Products and components are designed for reuse and high-value recycling, supported by available, proven recycling technologies and process routes.

Efficient secondary materials markets

Clear specifications and standards, predictable demand from end-users (e.g. panel manufacturers), and fair market conditions enable long-term investment in collection, sorting, and recycling capacity across the EU.

Secure high-quality supply at volume

Ensure that the maximum practicable share of recovered wood reaches material recycling streams as clean, well-characterised fractions, rather than being lost to disposal or low-value recovery.

Ensuring the availability of recovered wood has been identified as the priority. At present, the volumes available for fibre recycling and other high-quality applications are limited by quality losses due to mixing with other waste streams, use as a renewable energy source, and landfilling.

Multi-stakeholder dialogue instead of one-size-fits-all solutions

Across the EU, there are a plethora of wood waste market situations due to national and regional differences in legislation, generated volumes, collection and recycling, and the presence or lack of relevant industries. For this reason, instead of a one-size-fits-all approach to wood recycling, showcasing best practices from selected regions is key to identifying solutions that are transferable for other regions, while supporting decision-making on investments, incentives and subsidies. Hence, value networks, based on multi-stakeholder dialogue including all relevant actors on national, regional or local level must further develop these markets and enable a common understanding of the conditions required to keep secondary raw materials flowing to their highest-value long-term use. Ultimately, improved wood waste management enables an expansion of the overall material supply and benefits the entire forest-based sector (i.e. any industry depending on forests for their raw material requirement, e.g. woodworking, panel and furniture manufacturing, pulp and paper manufacturing and converting, etc.).

2.3 - METHODOLOGY

This Roadmap has been co-created by experts from industry and academia aiming to further stimulate the dialogue and provide systemic analysis and solutions, paving the way towards a wood-based circular economy. It builds on findings from discussions held during general assemblies, pilot system demonstrations, and webinars organised as part of the EcoReFibre project. To facilitate a more in-depth analysis, five onsite workshops and four external advisory board meetings (online) were dedicated to specific issues, such as recovered wood supply or research needs, between May 2023 and September 2025. Insights and assessments drawn from conversations and presentations at trade fairs, such as Ecomondo 2024 (Rimini, Italy) or LIGNA 2025 (Hanover, Germany), and conferences (e.g. 13th European Wood-based Panel Symposium 2024 in Hamburg, Germany) were also incorporated.

Chapter 4 is based on a review of the regulations and an analysis of the potential impacts on the wood-based panel industry, with a focus on the fibreboard industry using recycled fibres. Additional information was obtained by analysing the regulations within the framework of the EUFORE project (grant no. 01081788, 2022-2026) [20]. The implications of these regulations for the wood supply, as well as for the demand from the sawmill and the wood-based panel industries, were discussed in workshops with relevant stakeholders. Further details about the methodology and main results can be found in Kies et al. 2025 [21].

Among other sources, trade data collected by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) [22] and the Annual Reports of the European Panel Federation (EPF), e.g. [17] were used for EcoReFibre data modelling to estimate the volumes of MDF waste generated per year. The 'Catalogue of Wood Waste Classifications in the UNECE Region' [3] and 'Circularity concepts in forest-based industries' [23] also count among the most relevant references.

3

**STAKEHOLDER MAP OF
INDUSTRIES, POLICY MAKERS,
INITIATIVES, RELATED PROJECTS**

Numerous stakeholders are involved in recovered wood and fibreboard recycling, reflecting the complexity of material flows, market dynamics, and technological innovation across the sector. Each group of actors plays a distinct yet interconnected role in shaping the efficiency, sustainability, and circularity of wood-based products, whether through directly handling materials, driving demand or providing support e.g. analysis, consulting, funding, etc. Moreover, their relevance depends on local settings. For instance, in urban areas generating larger volumes, increased economies of scale favour investments in infrastructure. In other regions, where material loops are closed directly between furniture manufacturers and panel producers, centralised waste collection may be less needed. The following sections outline the primary, secondary, and tertiary stakeholders, highlighting their specific functions and influence.

In addition, a non-exhaustive overview of key stakeholders in the wood-based panel sector at the European level, including panel producers, collaborating institutes, and national associations, can be found on the [EPF website](#). A country-specific breakdown of the stakeholder landscape is available on the website's individual country pages (accessible by clicking the desired country).

3.1 - PRIMARY STAKEHOLDERS – DIRECTLY HANDLING MATERIAL

Wood-based panel producers (primarily MDF/HDF manufacturers)

WBP producers drive demand for recycled material and set quality requirements that influence upstream collection, sorting, and processing practices. Some panel manufacturers have developed their own infrastructure for collecting and processing recovered wood. By managing these operations internally, they can secure a reliable supply of suitable material and maintain control over quality and logistics.

Furniture industry

The furniture industry supplies significant volumes of clean manufacturing and processing residues. Further, their decisions regarding material selection, (circular) product design, and end-of-life strategies have a significant impact on the overall sustainability of the sector. Finally, post-consumer furniture products are transferred to the WBP industry as recovered wood.

Packaging industry

Solid wood, fibreboard, and other WBP are major components of packaging material (e.g. pallets, boxes, or vegetable crates). The packaging industry is both a material purchaser and supplier of industrial by-products suitable for recycling in wood products.

Construction industry

The construction industry is a significant generator of wood waste, from demolition, renovation and new construction activities. As a major consumer of wood-based products, its material choices and waste management practices directly influence the volume and quality of recovered wood available for recycling.

Collection and recycling infrastructure (public and private)

Wood waste is channelled into recycling through a dual system of public and private actors. Municipal collection and processing centres are responsible for collecting, sorting and pre-processing waste from households, bulky waste streams, and construction/demolition projects. In parallel, private recycling companies operate with greater specialisation and market orientation, upgrading post-consumer wood into consistent, quality-controlled feedstock for panel producers. Their effectiveness in segregating and preparing wood waste streams directly impacts the quality and availability of material for recycling, making them a key intermediary link in the circular economy for wood products.

Incineration or biomass plants

These facilities use wood waste primarily for energy recovery, excluding significant high-quality volumes from circular material use. Their demand influences market prices and availability of suitable supply for panel producers. Balancing the needs of energy recovery with the goals of material recycling is key for sustainable wood waste management.

3.2 - SECONDARY STAKEHOLDERS – ENABLE, SUPPORT, INFLUENCE THE PROCESS

Eco-organisations

Eco-organisations are national producer responsibility bodies (under EPR) that finance and organise separate collection, take-back, and treatment for specific product streams. Funded by eco-fees on products placed on the market, they contract municipalities and private platforms, setting acceptance and quality rules. Acting as intermediaries between producers, public authorities, and recyclers, they stabilise funding and standards, increase capture rates, channelling recovered fractions to high-value reuse and recycling. In some cases, they also provide R&I funding.

Technology and engineering solutions

Advanced technologies for wood recycling may be provided by single companies as end-to-end solutions or by complementary players across 3 categories:

- Industrial equipment manufacturers: design and produce specialised machinery for sorting, processing, and fibre extraction.
- Process engineering companies: develop efficient workflows and integrated systems for material recovery.
- Measurement technology and automation providers: enhance processes with advanced control systems and digital monitoring.

Adhesive manufacturers

The types of adhesives used in wood-based panels can significantly impact the feasibility and efficiency of recycling processes. Manufacturers who develop adhesives can contribute by developing formulations that are compatible with recycling technologies, or that allow for easier separation of wood fibres.

Industry associations

Industry associations represent and advocate for the collective interests of their members within the forest-based sector, engaging with policymakers and regulators. They play a role in shaping legislative and economic frameworks, coordinating joint initiatives, and setting industry standards. Among the key associations are, but not limited to:

EPF – European Panel Federation acts as a pan-European industry association, offering the wood-based panel sector a collective voice to navigate political, economic, and technical complexities. EPF advocates for the sector's role as an integral part of the EU's circular bioeconomy, supporting high standards among manufacturers while promoting wood waste uptake across Europe.

EFIC – European Furniture Industries Confederation serves as the central representative body for the European furniture industry. Its purpose is to unite national furniture associations and companies, providing a collective platform to address common challenges and opportunities within the EU context.

CEI-Bois – European Confederation of Woodworking Industries Brussels-based umbrella confederation bringing together 18 national organisations and 4 European sector federations. Promotes the European wood sector and its applications, represents and safeguards the woodworking industries' interests, and engages in EU policymaking.

Clusters, alliances and networks

Serving as bridgebuilders, clusters make research activities, policies, and regulations accessible for companies on national and regional level. By acting as multipliers for industry-specific information, such as technology advancements or raw material supply for fibreboard recycling, clusters ensure that knowledge, innovation, and best practices are disseminated to all stakeholders. Such knowledge transfer may also be supported through targeted trainings often co-organised with universities and other training providers.

Alliances like **Wood4Bauhaus** and **Circular Choices** unite a diverse range of actors from industry and research in the wood-based sector to encourage the sustainable development of the built environment aligning with EU initiatives.

InnovaWood is the European Network for wood research, innovation, and education, bringing together a large community of scientists, educators and experts. Its mission is to raise awareness, provide strategic guidance, advance education, foster innovation, and promote the integration of new technologies to enhance quality of life and support the forest-based sector in the transition to a sustainable bioeconomy.

Research organisations and universities

They drive innovation in sustainable recovered wood management, develop methods for sorting, processing, and valorising it, often in collaboration with the industry. Their work extends to optimising existing technologies, assessing environmental and economic impacts, and developing standards and best practices. They also educate and train future professionals and provide the research that often forms the foundation for evidence-based policymaking.

3.3 - TERTIARY STAKEHOLDERS – MARKET AND DEMAND SIDE

Dealers and retailers – furniture, interior design, DIY stores, artisans

They supply and market products while influencing their acceptance and promotion. They can also represent a valuable source of post-consumer wood by acting as collection points for used furniture and take-back schemes, making significant quantities of wood waste available for recycling while promoting consumer engagement.

Dealers and retailers – packaging

Wholesale markets, supermarkets, and other dealers and retailers handle significant amounts of packaging material. They can opt for utilisation of wood-based materials feeding into recovered wood supply for WBP.

Consumers

Cost, environmental awareness, product information: purchasing decisions of consumers drive the demand for recycled wood products. In turn, ecolabels, certifications, and public awareness campaigns influence and inform consumers about the benefits and characteristics of recycled wood products, thereby shaping market preferences and supporting sustainable practices.

3.4 - POLICY MAKERS

The policy landscape relevant to fibreboard recycling and circular value networks spans across multiple levels of governance, from the European Union down to regional and local authorities. Each level plays a distinct yet complementary role in shaping the regulatory framework, guiding investment, and steering the transition towards a more circular use of wood resources.

At the European level, the European Commission defines the overarching policy direction through its Directorates-General. DG Environment plays a central role by coordinating waste and recycling legislation, including the Waste Framework Directive, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and rules on transboundary waste shipments. DG Energy and DG Climate influence the balance between the material use of wood and its competing demand for energy production, whereas DG Grow supports industrial competitiveness, standardisation, and market development for secondary raw materials.

The European Parliament shapes legislation through its committees on environment, industry, and the internal market, while the Council of the EU represents Member State positions in the negotiation and adoption of legal acts. Supporting these institutions, the European Environment Agency provides monitoring and analysis, while European standardisation bodies such as CEN define the technical criteria that underpin market confidence in secondary raw materials.

At the national level, responsibility may vary but lies primarily with ministries of environment, which oversee the transposition and implementation of EU environmental directives. Equally important are ministries of energy and climate, which design renewable energy policies and subsidies that influence the competition between energy recovery and material recycling.

Ministries of economy and industry may further intervene by supporting innovation in manufacturing and promoting the bioeconomy. National parliaments set enabling measures, including extended producer responsibility schemes and fiscal incentives, while national standardisation bodies ensure alignment with EU requirements.

The sub-national level becomes especially relevant in federal and decentralised contexts, such as Germany, Spain, or Belgium. Regional governments and waste management agencies plan, permit, and operate collection and recycling infrastructure, and they can also channel regional funds into circular economy initiatives. Their decisions are often decisive for the availability and quality of wood waste locally.

Finally, at the local level, municipalities play a direct role in the collection of post-consumer wood through civic amenity sites, kerbside collection schemes, and municipal waste companies. Local permitting authorities influence the siting and operation of collection and recycling facilities. These frontline actors, although often overlooked, are crucial for ensuring that sufficient volumes of clean, sortable wood can be recycled into fibreboard rather than lost to low-value applications.

Taken together, the interaction of governance across the EU, national, regional, and local levels defines the enabling framework for circular fibreboard use. EU institutions set the overall legal framework and long-term ambitions, national governments transpose and adapt these rules into binding measures and incentives, regional authorities oversee infrastructure and investment programmes, and local actors are directly responsible for collection and treatment practices. Each of these levels plays a complementary role and aligning them through stronger coordination will be critical to unlocking the full circularity potential of wood waste in Europe.

3.5 - RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROJECTS

Wood waste management and fibreboard recycling is part of a general shift in wood research towards circular economy solutions over the last 10 years. This has gained further momentum through global supply chain bottlenecks and raw material price volatility triggered by the Covid-19 pandemic. While EcoReFibre focusses on recycling, wood related circular economy research covers topics such as the reduction and reuse of materials and products, bio-based adhesives and resins, circular businesses, and by extension, replacement of fossil-based materials and products. To provide a condensed overview on EcoReFibre related wood research projects, 23 projects (18 EU-funded, 5 nationally funded) have been listed in Annex 8.1. This list includes both completed and ongoing projects, focusing mainly on wood recycling, WBP and bio-based adhesives and resins. The desk research was conducted by consulting the CORDIS website, and InnovaWood's project database and Circular Economy group.

4

POLICY

CONTEXT

4.1 - OVERVIEW

The transition to a circular bioeconomy and the increased use of recycled wood fibres in wood-based products are both influenced by and contributing to a broad array of policies and strategic frameworks including the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the EU Bioeconomy and Forest Strategies. In line with these initiatives wood and fibre recycling aim to increase overall economic resilience, reduce environmental impacts, promote resource efficiency, and foster innovation in the use of secondary raw materials. This chapter provides a contextual overview of the most relevant policies, detailing their scope and potential or actual impacts on the fibreboard and wood recycling sectors.

The European policy landscape increasingly recognises the importance of recycled wood in a sustainable, circular economy. A combination of regulatory incentives (e.g. landfill restrictions, eco-design requirements), market-shaping policies (e.g. DPPs, public procurement), and innovation strategies (e.g. bioeconomy and forest strategies) is converging to support the uptake of recycled wood in panel products. However, challenges remain; ongoing dialogue with policymakers and early alignment with evolving standards will be essential to fully maximise the circular potential of fibreboards in the years ahead.

4.2 - KEY POLICIES FOR WOOD RECYCLING

This section presents the five policies considered most relevant for wood recycling. For completeness, additional 21 EU policies shaping circular use of wood and secondary raw material markets are listed in the Annex 8.2, providing brief notes on their scope, relevance and potential impacts, with references for further reading.

Waste Framework Directive (WFD) Directive 2008/98/EC [1]

The WFD is the European law on waste. It sets the waste hierarchy (prevention, preparing for reuse, recycling, other recovery such as energy, and disposal) and calls on Member States to establish separate collection where this improves recycling. It defines waste, industrial byproducts and when a material can cease to be waste once quality criteria are met (EndofWaste, EoW). It also establishes EPR as a policy tool, sets general recycling targets, and lays down rules on permitting, recordkeeping, and enforcement.

For the wood sector, the WFD matters in four main ways:

- **Separate collection and quality:** it pushes Member States to collect wood separately where this improves recycling, reducing contamination and improving the supply of clean, recycling grade wood for panels.
- **EndofWaste pathways:** it provides the legal route for recovered wood and wood fibres to exit “waste” status once they meet defined criteria (quality, environmental protection, market demand), enabling smoother trade and use in manufacturing.
- **EPR schemes:** it enables EPR for relevant product streams (e.g. furniture, packaging, construction products at national level), which can fund better collection, sorting, and quality improvements for wood waste.
- **Hierarchy and markets:** by prioritising material recycling over energy recovery, it underpins policies that keep suitable wood in higher value material loops before bioenergy, influencing gate fees, permits, and public procurement.

The Directive is in force (consolidated to 18/02/2024) and is expected to be updated under the Circular Economy Act agenda (cf. Annex 8.2) to streamline recycling and address fragmented national EPR schemes – changes that could further shape wood waste collection quality, crossborder movement via EoW recognition, and funding for recycling infrastructure.

Renewable Energy Directive (RED III) (EU) 2023/2413 [13]

RED III sets binding EU targets for renewable energy share and governs support schemes for bioenergy, sustainability and GHG criteria for biomass, and cascading use principles. It shapes how woody biomass can be incentivised, prioritised, and accounted for in energy markets.

Why it matters for wood recycling and fibreboard:

- Cascading principle and hierarchy: it calls on Member States to apply cascading use of biomass, i.e., prioritising material uses before energy, thereby supporting the retention of suitable wood waste in high-value recycling rather than diverting it to subsidised combustion.
- Support scheme design: it requires that public support for bioenergy avoids market distortions and over-incentivising use of quality wood that could be materially recycled.
- Sustainability/traceability rules: it establishes sustainability and GHG criteria and verification for biomass used in energy, indirectly improving transparency of wood flows that may compete with material recyclers.
- System planning: through national energy and climate plans (NECPs), it influences availability of woody feedstocks by shaping demand from energy plants. Alignment with WFD/ESPR policies is critical to safeguard recyclable fractions.

Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) (EU) 2024/1781 [14]

The ESPR is the EU's framework law for improving the sustainability and circularity of virtually all physical products placed on the EU market, replacing and expanding the old Ecodesign Directive beyond energy-related products. It empowers the Commission to set product-specific ecodesign requirements via delegated acts and creates an EU Digital Product Passport system.

Why it matters for wood and fibreboard:

- Future product rules: for furniture and related wood products, the forthcoming product requirements are expected to cover recycled content, durability, reparability, design for disassembly, and recyclability of composites/finishes – directly relevant to fibreboard.
- Digital Product Passport: it standardises product information (materials, recycled content, care/repair, end-of-life).
- Market pull: it measures on recycled content and designforrecycling in furniture/interiors increase demand for highquality recycled fibres and incentivises design compatible with end-of-life reuse and recycling.

Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation (PPWR), (EU) 2025/40 [15]

The PPWR regulates packaging design, recyclability, and recycled content across the EU. It harmonises the national measures and standards for packaging management to reduce packaging waste by promoting reuse, recycling and other forms of packaging waste valorisation. Affects paper packaging and wood packaging (pallets, crates).

Main impact on the wood sector:

- Wood-based packaging demand: by pushing recyclability and encouraging recycled/renewable materials, PPWR supports substitution away from difficult to recycle plastics toward recyclable wood-based solutions. It is expected to open new markets for secondary wood fibres from panel production, particularly in fibre-based packaging applications, and encourages circularity in cross-sector use of recycled wood.

Construction & Demolition Waste (CDW) Management Protocol [16]

The EU CDW Management Protocol is a non-binding guidance document aimed at improving the management of CDW across Member States by promoting selective demolition, better sorting, and higher-quality recycling. Updated in 2024, it provides practical recommendations for authorities, clients, designers, and contractors to plan and implement CDW prevention, on-site separation, and reliable quality assurance throughout the value chain.

Why it matters for the recyclability of wood fractions:

- Promotes selective demolition and improves sorting and logistics: encourages predemolition audits and material inventories, onsite segregation and appropriate containerisation, deconstruction practices to avoid quality degrading mixing, and clear acceptance criteria to enhance downstream recovery.

5

TECHNOLOGICAL AND MARKET DRIVERS AND BARRIERS

The market uptake of circular value networks using recovered wood, especially post-consumer fibreboard, is being shaped by a dynamic interplay of technological drivers, market demand, policy frameworks, and socio-economic trends. All factors influencing this transition are interdependent and change over time. Consequently, this causes shifts in supply chains, which in turn condition the economic viability of circular solutions. This chapter analyses these drivers and existing barriers drawing on the objectives and results of the EcoReFibre project to outline the key factors influencing the transition to circular solutions in the wood-based panel industry.

5.1 - MAIN DRIVERS

Strategic wood availability and resource security

The growing need to secure a stable and sustainable supply of raw materials is a key market driver. With increasing pressure on forests, climate change impacts, asymmetric competition from bioenergy and strong cross-sector competition for wood as a multi-purpose raw material (energy, chemicals, biofuels, packaging, etc.), the sector is seeking to reduce dependence on primary wood sources and to increase supply of recovered wood and other wood waste. The large, currently under-utilised resource of post-consumer fibreboard represents a significant opportunity to increase resilience and autonomy for the WBP industry, while supporting EU's circular economy, climate and biodiversity goals.

Technological advancements in collection, sorting, and recycling

A major challenge to circularity was the lack of commercially viable, industrial methods for recycling fibreboard. EcoReFibre and similar initiatives bridged this technological gap. Recent advancements in the collection, sorting, and processing of wood waste, such as AI-powered sorting systems, advanced sensor technologies, and improved dismantling and pre-processing methods, are enabling the efficient separation of fibreboard from mixed wood waste streams at an industrial scale.

Several innovations, i.e., a moisture modifying Thermo-Mechanical-Pulp process (mTMP), a steam-based technology and a dry impact reactor are being demonstrated within EcoReFibre to convert recovered fibreboard into high-quality fibres and fines. These recycled materials can then be used in the manufacturing of a range of products, including new MDF, HDF, particleboards, insulation materials, biocomposites, and construction blocks, enabling the substitution of considerable portions of virgin wood. Most importantly, this diversification of applications strengthens the market pull for recycled materials, while also raising recovery rates, improving material quality, and delivering cleaner secondary streams, which makes high-value recycling more feasible and cost-effective.

In parallel, the integration of machine learning and data analytics in process optimisation is a key enabler for cost and energy reduction, quality assurance, and scaling up recycling technologies. Digital tools also support better market data collection, traceability, and business model innovation.

Evolving business models and market demand

The rise of circular business models – such as product-as-a-service, take-back schemes, and EPR – has the potential for greater collection and recycling of wood products. New business models, such as using recovered wood in OSB and potentially even plywood manufacture or recycling companies that integrate advanced sorting and extraction technologies to recover high-quality fibres from recovered wood into their portfolio, can enable also smaller players to incorporate recycled materials into their products, further driving innovation and sustainability across the industry.

At the same time, there is growing market demand for products with recycled content, fuelled by consumer awareness, and corporate sustainability commitments, that can be further encouraged by green public procurement policies.

Policy and regulatory support

Ambitious EU and national policies – such as the Waste Framework Directive, Circular Economy Action Plan, and Green Deal – are driving demand for more recycling and sustainable materials by setting targets for recycling and circularity. At the same time in sectors like furniture and construction, the growing market demand from end-users for products with lower environmental impact and recycled content favours innovation and investment in the sector.

It is noteworthy, however, that for increasing circularity it is more effective to improve the overall capture, sorting, and return of wood from the diverse streams (packaging, municipal, construction and demolition, etc.) into high-value material loops, supported by cost-efficient collection systems and dedicated EPR schemes, than setting product-level targets for recycled wood content in new products, as the latter measure bears the risk of acting as a barrier in specific cases.

Socio-economic and environmental needs

Societal expectations for climate action, resource efficiency, and local job creation are shaping industry priorities. The circular use of recovered wood aligns with these needs, offering environmental benefits and supporting regional economies.

5.2 - MAIN BARRIERS

Regional disparities and local market conditions

- Variability in wood waste composition and quality across regions.
- Differences in local market structures and industry presence.
- Proximity (or lack thereof) to panel production plants.
- Regional disparities in recycling capacity.

The composition and quality of wood waste streams differ significantly from one region to another, influenced by local consumption patterns, industry structure, and the presence or absence of panel plants. In some areas, the market for recycled wood is too small or too dispersed, making collection and recycling economically unviable. Long transport distances further increase costs and reduce the feasibility of recycling, especially in regions with low population density or limited industrial activity. Regional disparities in recycling capacity also constrain the supply of suitable material for panel production, meaning that solutions that are effective in one region may not be applicable elsewhere. This complicates the development of harmonised strategies for wood waste collection and recycling.

Fragmented and inconsistent collection systems

- Disparate collection and sorting practices for different waste streams (furniture, construction & demolition, packaging).
- Inconsistent involvement of EPR organisations and civic amenities across countries.
- Lack of harmonised standards for collection, sorting, and product definitions.
- Insufficient collection infrastructure.

The heterogeneity of wood waste collection systems across countries, and even within regions, extends across streams and actors, taking markedly different forms for furniture, construction and demolition, and packaging. Furniture waste may be collected via civic amenities and sorted at recycling centres, or, in some countries, with the involvement of EPR and eco-organisations. Construction and demolition waste often follows a similar path, but with increasing EPR involvement in some areas. Packaging waste typically has the most established systems, involving civic amenities, recycling centres, and companies.

Both the fragmentation of wood waste collection systems and the insufficient collection infrastructure lead to inconsistent supply, quality, and traceability of recovered wood, thereby obstructing the steady flow of suitable material entering the recycling stream and its scale up.

Competition with energy recovery

- Biomass power plants, alternative fuel markets and other industry sectors compete for wood waste feedstock.
- Policy and subsidy frameworks often favour energy recovery over material recycling.
- Volatile prices for electricity can impact wood waste availability immediately.

A significant portion of collected wood waste is diverted to energy recovery, particularly in regions where biomass power plants are prevalent or where subsidies make burning more attractive than recycling. The competition for feedstock reduces the availability of high-quality wood for material recycling. Additionally, the supply of fines – small wood particles suitable for fibreboard production – has dropped due to both increased demand from alternative fuel markets and changes in shredding technology that produce fewer fines. This dynamic not only limits the feedstock available for recycling but also undermines the economic case for investing in advanced recycling technologies. The energy sector's demand for wood waste is aggravating the availability of supply for material use, undermining its strategic importance for circularity. Depending on the price for electricity, the amount of wood consumed by power plants can vary significantly and quickly, causing an immediate impact on wood waste availability.

Physical and logistical constraints

- Collection sites often lack the space and infrastructure for effective source separation and sorting.
- Variable storage conditions (e.g. uncovered storage) lead to inconsistent moisture content and material quality.
- Long distance for transport and logistical challenges due to the dispersed nature of wood waste streams.
- Outdated municipal collection sites not designed for current recycling needs.
- Heterogeneous nature of post-consumer wood, including variable particle sizes and traces of non-wood materials.
- CDW is particularly mixed with other materials (plaster, cement, etc.).

Many collection and recycling sites were not designed to handle the current volume and diversity of wood waste streams. Space constraints limit the ability to separate and store different types of wood, while uncovered storage exposes material to the elements, resulting in highly variable moisture content that complicates processing. The proximity of collection sites to panel plants and the structure of local markets also play a critical role in determining the most efficient approach to collection and recycling. Long distance transport and logistical hurdles can reduce the economic viability of recycling, especially in regions where waste streams are widely dispersed. The heterogeneous nature of post-consumer wood, with variable particle sizes and frequent admixture with non-wood materials, further complicates sorting and affects adversely the quality of recycled wood fractions.

Economic viability

- High costs across the value chain: transport, sorting, storage, and the need for covered containers all increase overall costs.
- Fluctuating supply and quality: the irregular availability and heterogeneous quality of wood waste, especially mixed and unclean CDW, drive up processing costs.
- Stringent quality requirements: fibreboard production requires high-purity feedstock, raising costs for sorting and cleaning.
- Uncertain investment environment: high upfront costs for new technologies and business models, coupled with sensitivity to raw material price fluctuations, undermine economic viability.
- Lack of harmonised standards: the absence of consistent criteria for secondary raw materials limits market confidence and uptake.

All in all, the economic viability of wood recycling is challenged by a range of cost factors, including transport, sorting, and storage. The availability and quality of wood waste can fluctuate seasonally and regionally, due to construction and renovation cycles, weather changes, activity of energy recovery plants, challenging a consistent delivery of suitable feedstock. Fibreboard production, in particular, requires high-purity input, which is costly to achieve when dealing with mixed or unclean waste streams – especially from construction and demolition sources. Limited space for containers and the need for covered storage add to already high operating costs.

At the same time, the absence of financial incentives, high upfront investment requirements, and uncertain returns discourage stakeholders from upgrading infrastructure or scaling up new technologies and business models. These challenges are compounded by the lack of harmonised standards for secondary raw materials, which undermines market confidence and uptake, making economic viability highly sensitive to fluctuations in raw material prices and technology costs.

6

RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PRIORITIES

The EcoReFibre achievements support the EU Commission's priority "A new plan for Europe's sustainable prosperity and competitiveness" and its "Competitiveness Compass" [24]. They further support the European Green Deal and contribute to Europe's sustainable growth through a more resilient circular economy in line with the upcoming EU Circular Economy Act [25]. Notably, EcoReFibre drives the uptake of innovative, circular and bio-based materials and value chains that play a key role for the defossilisation, climate neutrality and economic autonomy in line with the updated EU Bioeconomy Strategy and the New European Bauhaus.

EcoReFibre's progress in sorting of recovered wood and wood waste and fibre extraction has contributed to increasing industrial scale material circularity and economic resilience of wood-based panel manufacturers through sustainable secondary raw material supply. Yet, economic viability is conditioned by the maturity of technological solutions and the efficiency of secondary raw material markets in providing sufficient quantities of high-quality recovered wood on local and regional level. To further expand fibreboard recycling, research and innovation (R&I) need to be addressed in three areas:

- Efficient secondary raw material markets: identifying, improving and scaling circular value networks for wood waste across Europe.
- Data availability: improved data provision integrating material flows, specifications, and market information.
- Technology development: further enhancement and optimisation of technologies for wood waste sorting, fibre extraction and panel production using recycled fibres, incl. design-for-recycling principles for fibreboards.

6.1 - CIRCULAR VALUE NETWORKS ANALYSIS AND DEVELOPMENT

Rationale

As Europe advances a sustainable bioeconomy balancing defossilisation, climate neutrality and resource efficiency, recovered wood and wood waste markets are evolving rapidly. Circular value networks are intersectoral stakeholder networks operating at national, regional and local levels that shape these markets within existing legal frameworks. Their structures and governance vary across Europe, with well-known examples such as Rilegno (Italy) [26], OVAM (Flanders, [27; 28]) and France's EPR-based eco-organisations [29]. Yet, many others remain underdeveloped or invisible. Research is needed to reveal internal mechanisms, share best practices, and strengthen circularity within these networks.

R&I priorities

Map the research needs and develop recommendations to foster efficient wood and bio-based secondary raw material markets and circular value networks in relation to structures, governance, regulation, finance, and training. Given Europe's highly diverse wood waste markets, regional case studies should be analysed to identify best practices that can inform investment, incentives, and policy alignment. To achieve this, representative circular value networks must be studied in depth regarding waste origin and volumes, raw material composition, supply and logistical infrastructure and waste sorting and cleaning technologies, governance and stakeholder behaviour. Results should pinpoint optimal transition pathways for regional circularity hubs, enhance industrial symbiosis, and be disseminated through effective stakeholder engagement actions to maximise impact and foster innovation, investment and SME participation.

6.2 - IMPROVED AVAILABILITY OF MARKET DATA

Rationale

Availability of data is foundational for establishing secondary raw material markets. Today, data availability is inconsistent: information on material streams, end-uses (including energy recovery of post-consumer wood), prices and capacities remains fragmented across sectors and countries, with limited interoperability and uneven reporting.

This hampers reliable flow characterisation, matching of supply and demand, and planning of investments in sorting, logistics and upscaling. Differences in regulations, collection schemes, quality protocols and local industrial capacity further compound these gaps by creating incomparable datasets and regional blind spots in both the availability and quality of wood and fibreboard waste.

As Europe shifts from sectoral to more systemic, regional and local circular economies, there is a pressing need for integrated national datasets and harmonised indicators to quantify material and energy flows, ensure sufficient high-quality feedstock for recyclers and users, and build transparency, market trust and circularity in the bio-based economy. An important building block for better data collection and subsequently for a broader development of secondary raw material markets, is the adoption of specifications for defined, tradable wood waste grades and secondary raw materials. Section 6.3 provides further information on the benefits of such specifications.

R&I priorities

Develop interoperable data systems that integrate material and energy flows, and market information. Adopt digital traceability tools such as DPPs, RFID (Radio-frequency) or QR (Quick Response) identification, and in-line IoT (internet-of-things) monitoring devices, among others. Standardise data-exchange formats between stakeholders through data parametrisation where it helps building trust to enable accurate monitoring and benchmarking. Conduct regional case studies to quantify available wood waste fractions and barriers, assess infrastructure and transport feasibility, and evaluate economic and environmental benefits of improved information accessibility. Identify additional options for circular network development and build models to predict local wood waste composition and yields. Drive the digitalisation of the entire recycling process, linking data systems, monitoring tools and prediction models to provide reliable, ideally real-time, data for wood waste users, and to enable flexible distribution options and efficient supply-chain management and industrial symbiosis.

6.3 - SECONDARY RAW MATERIAL SPECIFICATIONS FOR MARKET DEVELOPMENT

Rationale

Specifications based on parameters such as category, composition, and particle size are essential to establish defined grades of wood waste as secondary raw materials. Secondary raw material specifications will foster market development by improving consistency and transparency. At the same time, specifications facilitate data collection, which is key for market research and the digitalisation of recycling processes aiming to improve wood waste allocation. Moreover, specifications support certification processes and facilitate compliance with end-of-waste criteria where applicable.

R&I priorities

Develop secondary raw material specifications for wood in a collaborative manner between the recycling, wood, and where appropriate energy sectors according to respective user needs while considering material availability and quality. Facilitate engagement and knowledge exchange to ensure broad participation of stakeholders. Ensure technical relevance and market alignment to accomplish practical specifications that are meaningful and accepted across the involved sectors and that can ideally be suitable for policy recommendations and regulations. Monitor and evaluate market adoption and impact and iterate for further improvement of specifications.

6.4 - IMPROVED SORTING FOR HIGH-VALUE RECYCLING

Rationale

Further research in the sorting of recovered wood needs to solve the identification of 'lookalikes' – particles that are often misclassified as MDF or HDF, such as linoleum, hardboard or thick pieces with a non-wood coating that are not suitable for fibre recovery. Removing these materials before the defibration step increases the efficiency of the fibre recycling process. In EcoReFibre's material characterisation work, up to 16% of the analysed fibreboard fractions were composed of hardboard. This non-representative value was derived from an initial assessment of the composition of recovered wood, as data on volumes and types of wood products in waste streams is scarce. Continued advances in sorting are essential to apply the cascading principle effectively and to tailor recovered wood for diverse high-value applications.

R&I priorities

Further exploit the potential of sophisticated sorting technologies that combine advanced NIR-sensors and/or RGB-cameras¹ with AI and deep learning approaches. Paired with efficient defibration methods, they represent key enabling technologies for fibreboard recycling on an industrial scale. Such advanced sorting systems have entered the market since a few years only and still hold an immense potential for improved accuracy and material recognition.

6.5 - PROCESS CONTROL AND OPTIMISATION FOR SECONDARY MATERIALS

Rationale

Recovered wood is highly variable in properties like density, moisture content, and adhesive type. In particular fibreboard encompasses a range of panel sub-types with different degrees of recyclability depending on their composition and production processes. Real-time material characterisation is essential to adapt processing steps such as pretreatment and defibration for improved fibre yield, quality, and process efficiency.

R&I priorities

Identify and prioritise key material parameters to monitor across the entire process, from pretreatment and defibration to fibre cleaning, drying, and glueing. By extension, this may include assessing whether existing characterisation technologies and sensor systems used in WBP manufacture require optimisation to meet the specific needs of fibre recycling and secondary material use.

(1) NIR-sensors are based on Near Infrared spectroscopy. They are widely used for industrial applications, among many others to determine the moisture content of a material or the type of plastic an object is made of. RGB-cameras capture light of red, green, and blue wavelengths thus providing colour and texture information similar to human vision.

6.6 - DESIGN-FOR-CIRCULARITY PRINCIPLES

Rationale

Around 43% of recovered fibreboard panels carried varnishes, films, or impregnated papers that must be removed to avoid quality losses in recycling. Although current cleaning steps such as sifting are efficient, more insight is needed into coating types, prevalence, and related contamination risks. Coatings that are removable in one piece and the use of de-bondable adhesives could reduce cleaning needs and support furniture reuse. De-bondable adhesives for finishes may soon reach industrial feasibility, but those for binding fibreboards remain at low TRL.

R&I priorities

Improving coating removal requires determining the optimal shredding size of wood waste, as it affects coating particle size and sifting efficiency. Broader use of paper-based coatings which do not hinder processing should also be explored, supported by Europe-wide sampling to map coating types and contamination risks.

In addition, R&I should further advance de-bondable adhesives for fibreboard binding, as they can enable softer defibration, save energy, and preserve fibre quality for multiple recycling cycles. Continued work on design-for-recycling principles is essential for establishing sustainable, circular materials. Given the time needed for R&I activities plus a lifespan of fibreboards of about 12 years on average as determined within EcoReFibre, neither removable coatings nor de-bondable panel adhesives will have major short-term or mid-term effects. Nonetheless, the findings will advance long-term circularity and resource efficiency by enabling high-quality fibre recovery with reduced energy input.

6.7 - INCREASING THE SHARE OF RECYCLED FIBRES

Rationale

Target values for shares of recycled fibres in fibreboards range between 10 % and 30 % today, with the aim of increasing them further. As knowledge advances and these technologies demonstrate proven feasibility and scalability, WBP manufacturers will be able to determine the necessary adjustments in their installations to progressively expand fibre recycling capacity, and to incorporate higher percentages of recycled fibres into their boards.

R&I priorities

Higher shares of recycled fibres in boards are feasible, as demonstrated in laboratory tests. Combined with further fibre characterisation, machine learning supported process optimisation and development, industrial trials are required to confirm that economic and quality requirements such as adhesive content and mechanical properties are met in large scale manufacturing.

7

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS TO BOOST WOOD WASTE CIRCULARITY

From a macroeconomic, environmental, and societal perspective, keeping wood in material loops delivers the greatest overall added value: it preserves embedded carbon in new products, strengthens EU’s circular bioeconomy, and reduces pressure on virgin resources. In line with the WFD’s hierarchy and RED III’s emphasis on material use before energy recovery, EcoReFibre focuses on scaling high-quality recycling of wood and fibreboard waste so that these secondary raw materials can flow back into manufacturing while preserving their highest value. To make this happen at scale, three mutually reinforcing conditions must be met:

1. Design for circularity

Products and components are designed for reuse and high-value recycling, supported by available, proven recycling technologies and process routes.

2. Efficient secondary-materials markets

Clear specifications and standards, predictable demand from end-users (e.g. panel manufacturers), and fair market conditions enable long-term investment in collection, sorting, and recycling capacity across the EU.

3. Secure high-quality supply at volume

Ensure that the maximum practicable share of wood waste reaches material recycling streams as clean, well-characterised fractions, rather than being lost to disposal or low-value recovery.

Today, the European wood-based panel industry is partway there to achieving these goals. Particleboard amounts to 53% of the total European WBP production and already incorporates high shares of recovered wood (48%) [17]. EcoReFibre, with its recent technological advancements in wood waste sorting and recycling technologies, extends this proven circularity to MDF that has an annual European production volume of around 11 million m³ [17]. Indeed, by unlocking reliable recovery pathways that enable fibreboard and other wood wastes to be recycled into new fibreboard products, EcoReFibre contributes to fulfil condition 1 mentioned above.

The remaining gaps persist at the system level: across Europe, secondary raw material markets and infrastructures are only partly designed for a circular bioeconomy. The fulfilment of the above-mentioned conditions 2 and 3 requires substantial adjustments and setup of decentralised multi-stakeholder networks for higher value creation that optimise the use of secondary raw materials and close material loops early. A sustained dialogue across the value network is then essential, linking waste holders, collectors, sorters, logistics providers, recyclers, panel manufacturers, brands, municipalities and regulators, as to enable a common understanding of the conditions required to keep secondary raw materials flowing to their highest-value use.

Ultimately, improved wood waste management enables an expansion of the overall material supply and benefits the entire forest-based sector.

The following sections outline targeted policy recommendations that operationalise these goals.

7.1 - INCREASING THE QUANTITY OF WOOD WASTE COLLECTED

Mobilising wood waste collection and recycling

Challenge

A significant increase in wood-waste collection is the essential first step to unlock the full potential of recycling and circularity. Only with a significantly higher volume of collected wood waste can the efficient sorting, logistics, and recycling schemes be developed and optimised (material quality issues are addressed in section B). To achieve these foundational steps, a balanced mix of measures that work with local realities is required. An integrated approach would expand volumes across all streams, lower transport and carbon, and keep economic value and jobs within the EU.

Recommendations for policy measures

- Increase wood-waste collection as a top priority to expand the volume available for material recycling across all streams. Encourage Member States to design and adopt flexible collection and sourcing approaches that reflect local market structures. Where feasible, set ambitious yet realistic recycling targets to drive sustained capture growth, monitoring outcomes to assess whether a later, proportionate harmonisation of collection systems would add value.
- Incentivise producer take-back and reverse logistics so that furniture and construction product manufacturers arrange the return of post-consumer wood to panel producers/recyclers, enabling direct material recycling and closing the loop between product and raw material supply, e.g. under EPR schemes.
- Provide incentives or support mechanisms for local authorities, waste operators, and businesses to invest in infrastructure and logistics for increased wood waste collection.

Prioritising material use of wood over energy recovery

Challenge

To maximise the circular use of wood resources, it is essential to ensure that high-quality wood fractions are prioritised for material recycling before energy recovery. This aligns with cascading principle of the RED III Directive, which prioritises wood-based products, reuse, and recycling ahead of bioenergy, reserving energy recovery for cases where no economically viable or environmentally appropriate material use exists. In parallel, accelerating alternative renewables relieves pressure and competition on suitable fractions of woody biomass for higher-value material uses. Mandating the separation and diversion of suitable wood for material use allows for increased recycling rates and resource use optimisation.

Recommendations for policy measures

- Recalibrate public support to avoid distorting competition with the material sectors.
- Implement the cascading use principle of the RED III Directive: “prioritise material uses with a view to ensuring that woody biomass is used according to its highest economic and environmental added value in the following order of priorities: (a) wood-based products; (b) extending the service life of wood-based products; (c) reuse; (d) recycling; (e) bioenergy; and (f) disposal”.
- Adjust the deployment of alternative renewable energy sources, such as solar, wind, geothermal and non-woody biomass to reduce heat and electricity demand from woody biomass, to align with the EU’s energy transition goals.

Optimising storage for consistent wood supply

Challenge

Adequate and flexible storage capacity at recycling and collection sites is essential for the efficient management of wood waste and to buffer substantial seasonal fluctuations in supply and demand. Regulatory frameworks should be adapted to local market conditions, fire safety requirements, and stakeholder needs.

Recommendations for policy measures

- Increase allowable storage limits for operators with the technical capability to assess quality, avoid fire risk and channel high-quality fractions to material recycling. Additionally, allow for temporary or flexible storage solutions (such as modular storage or covered outdoor areas). This enables the management of seasonal peaks in the generation of wood waste, thereby preventing significant quantities from being excluded from value creation.

7.2 - UPGRADING THE QUALITY OF COLLECTED STREAMS

Modernising collection and sorting technologies

Challenge

To maximise the quality and value of wood waste fractions, it is essential to modernise collection systems and integrate advanced sorting technologies at the earliest stages of the process. The goal is to reduce material mixing, improve sorting efficiency, and lower operational costs, thereby enabling a robust and economically viable recycling value.

Recommendations for policy measures

- Maximise the recovery of recyclable wood waste through targeted pre-processing and dismantling (furniture) and selective demolition (construction/renovation), paired with mandatory or incentivised separate collection at municipal and commercial levels. Implement dedicated streams with advanced containers and clear labelling, high-control methods at civic amenity sites, and embed these requirements in public procurement, building codes, and demolition permits to ensure early differentiation and minimise mixing.
- Mandate that EPR funds are reinvested in the continuous improvement of collection systems, prioritising the recovery of recyclable wood waste at or near the source to improve resource efficiency and support the development of secondary material markets.
- Support the deployment and scaling-up of AI-supported and sensor-based sorting technologies through targeted funding, public-private partnerships, or regulatory requirements.

Efficient delivery of recyclable wood to material reusers

Challenge

Separately collected wood waste often loses value when first handled by operators without the technical capability to assess quality and channel high-quality fractions to material recycling. To safeguard quality and maximise circular value, public guidance for municipalities and large waste holders should set a preferable follow-up destination – qualified material producers, such as panel manufacturers, who are the main downstream user of recovered wood. Positioning technically capable operators at the front of the chain improves consistency for civic amenities and reduces leakage to lower-value uses.

Recommendations for policy measures

- Recognise all qualified facilities for material use of wood waste, such as wood-based panel manufacturers, as “wood waste competence centres” and set them as the preferred destination for separately collected recyclable wood waste. These competences include:
 - to assess, clean, and grade the incoming streams against agreed quality criteria;
 - prioritise allocation of recyclable fractions to material recycling routes.

8
ANNEX

8.1 - RELATED PROJECTS

To provide a condensed overview on EcoReFibre related wood research projects, 23 projects (18 EU-funded, 5 nationally funded) have been listed here below ordered by date. This list includes both completed and ongoing projects, focusing mainly on wood recycling, WBP and bio-based adhesives and resins. The desk research was conducted by consulting the CORDIS website, and InnovaWood's project database and Circular Economy group.

PROJECT NAME	FUNDING	DURATION	PROJECT SCOPE	KEYWORDS
WOODTREAT	Horizon Europe	2025-2029	Tackles the problem of preservative-treated wood waste by using automated sorting and cleaning methods to turn hazardous wood into safe, useful products.	Treated wood waste, recycling
SUSPENSE	Horizon Europe	2025-2029	Developing bio-based adhesives from renewable feedstocks, the project replaces harmful fossil-based adhesives in wood panels and insulation, improving performance, circularity, and reducing CO2 emissions.	Bio-based adhesives
SUSBOARD	Horizon Europe	2025-2029	Development of a 100% bio-based, formaldehyde-free adhesive. SUSBOARD aims to replace fossil-based chemicals in particleboards and MDF, enabling sustainable, industrial-scale wood board production.	Bio-based adhesive, wood-based panels
CIRCULAR-C	Horizon Europe	2025-2029	Development of bio-based adhesives, coatings, and fibres for wood panels using biomass residues and reversible chemical bonds. The project enhances recyclability, reduces hazardous chemicals, and lowers emissions, with industrial testing and Digital Product Passports supporting market uptake.	Bio-based adhesives
BIOGLUE: COMPETENCE CENTRE FOR BIO-BASED ADHESIVES	Vinnova	2023-2028	Creation of a world-leading research environment on bio-based adhesives, uniting the furniture, packaging, and construction sectors around shared challenges. The project represents an opportunity to drive sustainable innovation in a market covering 25% of global adhesive production.	Bio-based adhesives, sustainable innovation
WOOD2WOOD	Horizon Europe	2024-2027	Transformative valorisation: recycling and upcycling of contaminated wood waste from construction, demolition and furniture, into high-value products.	Wood waste
VIORBOND	Horizon 2020	2021-2027	Production of phenolic resins partially from lignin. Viobond substitutes fossil-based raw materials with sustainable alternatives for plywood, adhesives, and insulation, demonstrating both the production process and a viable European business model.	Phenolic resin, lignin
ALTHOLZDIALOG	German Federal Ministry of Food and Agri-culture	2024-2026	Developing standards, certifications, and labels to improve quality and trust in waste-wood products. It engages all actors in the value chain to boost transparency, consumer awareness, and the market for recycled wood.	Waste-wood product standards
INGUMA	Horizon Europe	2024- 2027	Developing biobased materials, including functionalised fibres, mycelium-based and wood fibre-based insulation, bio-based adhesives for plywood, green roof substrate, SIP construction panels.	Biobased, construction, fibres, mycelium, adhesives
ATRIUM	Horizon Europe	2024- 2027	Development of bio-based materials combining natural fibres, bioplastics and mycelium-based biotechnology. Terrace decking, flooring tiles, acoustic panels, green walls, and building blocks	Biobased, construction, fibres, mycelium, adhesives

PROJECT NAME	FUNDING	DURATION	PROJECT SCOPE	KEYWORDS
TIMBERLOOP	FOREST FUND, BMLUK	2022-2025	Development of strategies to recycle construction timber and preserve its quality for reuse in new products. Solid wood is recycled, and by-products from solid wood (EoL) are used to produce particle boards, which can also be recycled, keeping wood in circulation for longer.	Timber recycling, particle-boards
CISUFLO	Horizon 2020	2021-2025	Minimise the environmental impact of the EU flooring sector by a systemic framework for circular, sustainable floor coverings with technical feasibility and socio-economic factors. Includes wood laminated flooring.	Flooring
RESOURCE-EFFICIENT AND NON-TOXIC MATERIAL FLOWS FROM WOOD WASTE	Formas	2021-2023	Development of an automated online system to identify chemically contaminated wood waste	Contamina-ted wood
SWOP	Horizon 2020	2019-2023	Development of a 100% bio-based, recyclable, and non-toxic resin. The project replaces formaldehyde-based binders in wood panels, cutting carbon emissions and supporting safer, sustainable production.	Bio-based resin, wood-based panels
BIOFLEX	Horizon 2020	2020-2022	Transforming underutilised wood waste into cellulose and lignin, Bioflex diverts material from landfills and incineration, enabling new value chains and creating high-value products from contaminated or unwanted wood.	Wood waste, bio-based products
NOVEL STARCH-BASED ADHESIVE SYSTEMS TO ENABLE RECYCLING OF FIBREBOARDS	Vinnova	2020-2022	Fibreboards with bio-based components designed for circularity.	Starch-based adhesives, fibreboard recycling
HONEXT	Horizon 2020	2018-2021	Developing a fully recyclable fibreboard made from 100% cellulose waste, Honext replaces MDF with a VOC-free alternative that can be reused to produce new panels, supporting circularity and reducing reliance on virgin materials.	Recyclable fibreboard, circularity
WOODCIRCUS	Horizon 2020	2018-2021	Increases knowledge, raises awareness, and improves conditions for uptake of resource-efficient processing and recycling in wood-based value chains.	Wood recycling, resource efficiency
ECOBULK	Horizon 2020	2017-2021	“Closing the loop” of composite products in automotive, furniture, and building sectors by promoting greater reuse, refurbishment, and recycling of products, parts, and materials.	Composite recycling, product circularity
MATERIALIZE.X	Horizon 2020	2018-2018	Developing a bio-based adhesive for engineered wood, the project replaces formaldehyde-based adhesives with a safe, regulatory-compliant alternative and provides software to support its industrial integration.	Bio-based adhesive, engineered wood
GREEN BOARD	Horizon 2020	2018-2018	Production of high-quality wooden products from recycled old wood. Green Board increases recycling rates, reduces costs, and creates durable, customised, and sustainable furniture while supporting resource efficiency.	Recycled wood, furniture
FIBRECARB	Horizon 2020	2017-2018	Upcycling MDF waste into high-quality activated carbon and renewable energy, the project transforms low-value wood waste into sustainable, high-value products while reducing landfill disposal.	MDF waste, upcycling

8.2 - RELEVANT POLICIES

Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) (EU) 2024/3012 [30]

Scope: EU's first voluntary certification system for carbon removals, encompassing carbon storage in products. It aims to establish a robust and transparent framework for certifying high-quality carbon removal activities across the EU.

Status: In force. Adopted in 2024. Delegated acts forthcoming including on EU certification methodology for carbon storage in buildings.

Relevance: Recognizes temporary carbon storage in long-lasting products, such as wood-based construction materials, as a valid carbon removal activity. Specifically, it includes carbon storage activities that capture and store carbon in durable products for at least 35 years.

Potential Impact: By certifying the carbon storage potential of harvested wood products, the CRCF provides a mechanism to quantify and reward the climate benefits of using wood in construction. This could incentivize the use of recycled wood fibres in fibreboard production, promoting the circular bioeconomy and contributing to the EU's climate neutrality goals.

Chemicals Industrial Package and REACH Revision [31]

Scope: Package of legislative measures on chemicals, including REACH and legacy additives.

Status: Announced. Expected in 2025.

Relevance: Legacy substances in wood waste, such as formaldehyde or flame retardants, are regulated under REACH. Restrictions or clarifications may impact the recyclability of certain post-consumer wood.

Potential Impact: Clear, proportionate rules on legacy additives could facilitate safe recycling of wood waste without creating unmanageable regulatory burdens for fibreboard manufacturers.

Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) [32] and Circular Economy Act (CEA) [25]

Scope: Overarching EU strategy to boost circular practices across all sectors.

Status: CEAP adopted in 2020. CEA expected Q4 2026, public consultation launched in 08/2025.

Relevance: CEAP underpins legislative efforts like the ESPR and CPR. The CEA aims to resolve practical challenges in circular value networks, including barriers to waste circulation and fragmented EPR schemes. Overall, the objective is to double the EU's circularity rate by 2030 and establish a single market for secondary raw materials.

Potential Impact: If well implemented, the CEA could level the playing field between virgin and recycled wood, strengthen internal market mechanisms for circular materials, and simplify regulatory frameworks.

Climate neutrality (EU) 2021/1119 [33]

Scope: Strategies for climate change adaptation to comply to reduce net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. Forests are considered a tool for the decarbonisation of industries/sectors supported by investment in green technology.

Status: In force, amending 401/2009 and (EU) 2018/1999: European Climate Law

Relevance: Focus on forest carbon sinks and industries that can help to store carbon in products, such as the wood industry.

Potential impact: Focusing on forest carbon sinks could limit harvesting and raise costs, reducing the available wood supply. Recycled wood would be, therefore, an alternative to raw materials. Reversely, a focus on carbon storage in construction products will boost the use of wood and wood products.

Construction Products Regulation (CPR) (EU) 2024/3110 [34]

Scope: Sets performance, environmental and sustainability requirements for construction products. Digitalisation of information about environmental, structural, health and safety performance in Digital Product Passports. Harmonise and update technical standards (EN) and create new ones when needed.

Status: In force, repealing (EU) 305/2011. Revised in 2025. Standardisation ongoing.

Relevance: All the EN standards for the product area “Wood-based panels”, like those related to fibreboards used in construction, are covered. New reporting requirements via the Digital Product Passport and potential resource efficiency criteria are highly relevant.

Potential Impact: Future harmonised standards (e.g. revised EN 13986) may favour panels with higher recycled content and lower environmental impacts, thus stimulating fibreboard recycling.

Corporate sustainability reporting (EU) 2025/794 [35]

Scope: EU companies must ensure transparency by reporting on social and environmental impacts of their commercial activities.

Status: In force, amending (EU) 2022/2464 and (EU) 2024/1760.

Relevance: Stricter rules for polluting emissions, assessment, monitoring and compliance with environmental standards for all commercial activities and industries.

Potential impact: Wood-based panel industry, based on both raw material and recycled wood, could compete well with other more polluting industries in the construction and furniture sectors.

Energy Performance of Buildings (EPB) (EU) 2024/1275 [36]

Scope: Achieve a decarbonised real estate stock with zero emissions by 2050, reducing both construction and operational greenhouse gas emissions in buildings.

Status: In force.

Relevance: Focused on construction, the EPB encourages the use of sustainable materials and potential carbon storage products, which include wood and wood fibres.

Potential impact: Growing demand for more sustainable materials (wood fibres) and wood-based panels for building insulation.

EU Bioeconomy Strategy [37]

Scope: Aims to accelerate the development of a circular, sustainable bioeconomy.

Status: Implemented in 2012 and updated in 2018. New update expected in Q4 2025.

Relevance: Recognises wood recycling as a strategic area for biomass efficiency. Encourages innovation in bio-based industries.

Potential Impact: Can mobilise research funding and industrial support for fibreboard innovation, especially when linked with Horizon Europe and CBE JU (Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking) calls.

EU Forest Strategy for 2030 [38]

Scope: Promotes sustainable forest management and optimal use of forest resources.

Status: Adopted in 2021.

Relevance: Emphasises cascading use of wood and material-first principles, supporting the recycling of wood into products like fibreboard before energy recovery.

Potential Impact : Provides a policy basis to promote secondary fibre use in fibreboards and supports long-term sustainability of the wood sector.

EU Taxonomy (EU) 2021/2139 [39] and (EU) 2020/852 [40]

Scope: Technical screening criteria for determining the conditions under which an economic activity qualifies as contributing substantially to climate change mitigation or climate change. A voluntary market information tool to establish a sustainable investment framework through the creation of a classification system, or ‘taxonomy’, which defines environmentally sustainable economic activities.

Status: (EU) 2121/2139 in force, supplementing (EU) 2020/852. Current consolidated version: 08/01/2025.

Relevance: The wood industry, based on resources obtained from sustainable forest management practices, can in most cases be considered as environmentally sustainable economic activities. The wood industry, based on recycled wood, has the potential to be even more sustainable.

Potential impact: The taxonomy criteria in wood construction and furniture can open opportunities to attract investments, in environmental reporting or marketing.

Industrial emissions (EU) 2024/1785 [41]

Scope: Reduce industrial pollution and waste by implementing environmental permits, enforcing compliance measures, and suspending operations that repeatedly fail to meet environmental standards.

Status: In force, amending 2010/75/EU and 1999/31/EC

Relevance: Reduce industrial waste, including wood industries.

Potential impact: Reduction of industrial waste will enhance the use of by-products and recycled wood in the wood-based panels industry.

Landfill Directive 1999/31/EC [42]

Scope: Aims to minimise landfilling of biodegradable and recyclable waste.

Status: Adopted in 1999. In force. Current consolidated version: 04/08/2024.

Relevance: Wood, being biodegradable, is targeted under landfill diversion goals. Several Member States have already introduced landfill bans or taxes on wood waste.

Potential Impact: Promotes the diversion of wood from landfill to material recovery, increasing the availability of recycled fibre.

LULUCF (EU) 2018/841 [43]

Scope: The net land carbon removal of 310 Mt CO₂e by 2030 obligates the development of national forest accounting plans detailing emissions/sequestration, carbon pools, GHG, and sustainable management.

Status: In force, current consolidated version: 11/05/2023.

Relevance: Although it focuses on forests, it will impact wood supply.

Potential impact: To ensure GHG emissions reduction, forest management decisions could take the direction to limit harvest intensity, limiting the available wood for production. An industrial activity focused on recycled wood, such as recycled fibreboards, would be an alternative in case of a limited wood supply.

National Circular Economy Strategies and EPR Systems

Scope: Member State-specific roadmaps and regulatory frameworks implementing EU circular economy goals.

Status: Varies by country.

Relevance: Many countries have adopted specific targets or measures for wood waste recycling. EPR schemes for furniture or construction materials are emerging in countries like France and Germany.

Potential Impact: Well-designed EPR systems could provide financing for collection and pre-treatment infrastructure, enhancing the supply and quality of recycled wood.

Nature Restoration Law (EU) 2024/1991 [44]

Scope: Implementation of effective restoration measures to cover at least 20% of terrestrial and marine areas by 2030 and all degraded ecosystems by 2050. Monitoring key forest ecosystem indicators such as deadwood, forest structure, bird populations, or soil carbon.

Status: In force.

Relevance: Stricter harvesting regulations prioritising low-impact cutting methods may reduce wood supply but enhance other forest ecosystem services.

Potential impact: Limited access to raw material or by-products from the sawmill industry, encouraging the use of recycled wood for wood-based panels manufacturing.

New European Bauhaus (NEB) [45]

Scope: Cross-sectoral initiative promoting new ways of thinking and designing the built environment. It is based on three main values (beautiful, sustainable, and together) and three main principles (transdisciplinary, participatory, and multi-level engagement).

Status: Ongoing since 2021. Supported through various EU programmes with several pilot projects underway across Europe.

Relevance: Supports the use of natural, renewable, and bio-based materials, such as wood, in construction and renovation. It places emphasis on circular design, material efficiency, and low-carbon construction methods, which aligns closely with the objectives of the EcoReFibre project.

Potential Impact: By encouraging a shift toward regenerative and circular building practices, the NEB can stimulate demand for sustainable materials like fibreboards made from recycled wood.

Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 [46]

Scope: Controls POPs in products and waste to ensure safe management and disposal.

Status: In force. Current consolidated version: 04/08/2025

Relevance: Wood-based panels may contain substances such as formaldehyde or pentachlorophenol. Ensuring that recycled wood meets POPs thresholds is essential for legal compliance.

Potential Impact: May increase costs and complexity of recycling contaminated wood, but also promotes higher safety standards and consumer confidence in recycled materials.

Safe and sustainable by design - Commission recommendation 2022/2510 [47]

Scope: Development of a common understanding of what safe and sustainable chemicals and materials are and how to assess them.

Status: Revision. Guidance report version 2 planned in February 2026.

Relevance: Establishing a European assessment framework for 'safe and sustainable by design' (SSbD) chemicals and materials. The SSbD framework is a voluntary approach to guide the innovation process for chemicals and materials.

Potential Impact: Steering the innovation process in the transition towards clean and sustainable industries. Substitute or minimise the production and use of substances of concern. Minimise the impact on health, climate and the environment during sourcing, production, use and end-of-life of chemicals, materials and products.

Strategy for Housing Construction (Affordable Housing Initiative) [20], [48]

Scope: EU-level strategy to promote sustainable and affordable housing. It is included in the European Commission’s Renovation Wave Strategy and is a flagship of the New European Bauhaus (NEB).

Status: Presented in an info session in 2021, updated info in 2023. Publication expected in early 2026.

Relevance: Encourages modern, circular construction approaches, including the use of sustainable materials, nature-based solutions, and recycled construction materials such as fibreboards made with recovered wood.

Potential Impact: Could support market uptake of recycled-content panels through public procurement, housing renovation programmes, and green building incentives.

Waste Shipment Regulation (WSR) (EU) 2024/1157 [49]

Scope: Regulates intra- and extra-EU shipments of waste.

Status: in force. Current consolidated version: 09/01/2025. Revised in 2024, amending (EU) (EU) 1257/2013 and 2020/1056, and repealing 1013/2006. From 21 May 2026, digital systems will fully replace paper procedures.

Relevance: Simplified shipment of non-hazardous wood waste is essential for recyclers sourcing material from across borders. Overly restrictive procedures could fragment the secondary wood market.

Potential Impact: The regulation’s “green list” and streamlined notification requirements for non-hazardous waste like sorted wood waste could enhance cross-border flows and access to recycled input streams.

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